

SOCIAL AND EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS OF NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020: A BOON OR BANE

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Abstract:

The ministry of education, India has presented a new national education policy (NEP), 2020 after the last education policy in 1986. For a country like India with around 1.3 billion people, it is certainly an important revolutionary. It would not be an overstatement to say that the correct education policies can change the future of the entire country. At the policy draft level, it looks strong, however, the implementation systems will actually define the strength of the context. An attempt is made here to explore the possibilities of NEP as boon or bane by taking into consideration the national curricular and pedagogical framework, reforms to be implemented, emphasis on mother tongue/regional language for English-medium schools, plans of the government to open up higher education to foreign companies along with privatization, liberalization and globalization in general. Moreover, an attempt is made to suggest that government must facilitate the process of society's capacity to meet its own educational needs rather than strangle its ability to improvise, invent, and innovate.

Keywords: *National curricular and pedagogical framework, NEP reforms, emphasis on mother tongue, plans of government, Privatization, Liberalization And Globalization.*

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Introduction:

The National Education Policy (NEP) is a comprehensive framework to guide the development of education in the country. A new policy usually comes along every few decades. The latest policy is India's third. This new National Education Policy (NEP), 2020 aims for universalization of education from pre-school to secondary level with 100 per cent Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in school education by 2030 and to raise GER in higher education to 50 per cent by 2025.

The government plans to set up subject-wise committees with members from relevant ministries at both the central and state levels to develop implementation plans for each aspect of the NEP. The plans will list out actions to be taken by multiple bodies, including the HRD Ministry, state Education Departments, school Boards, NCERT, Central Advisory Board of Education and National Testing Agency, among others. Planning will be followed by a yearly joint review of progress against targets set.

The NEP proposes sweeping changes including opening up of Indian higher education to foreign universities, dismantling of the UGC and the All-India Council for Technical Education (AICTE), introduction of a four-year multidisciplinary undergraduate programme with multiple exit options, and discontinuation of the M Phil programme. NEP, 2020 is explored as a boon or bane by taking into consideration the following key aspects:

- national curricular and pedagogical framework,
- reforms to be implemented,
- emphasis on mother tongue/regional language for English-medium schools,
- people in transferable jobs, or children of multilingual parents,
- advantages and disadvantages for teachers,
- government plan to open up higher education to foreign companies,
- privatization, liberalization and globalization.

National Curricular, Pedagogical Framework And Reforms To Be Implemented:

NEP, 2020 promises to bring two crores out of school children back into the main stream. The 10+2 structure of school curricula is to be replaced by a 5+3+3+4 curricular structure corresponding to ages 3-8, 8-11, 11-14, and 14-18 years respectively. It will include 12 years of schooling and three years of Anganwadi and pre-schooling. NCERT will develop a National Curricular and Pedagogical Framework for Early Childhood Care and Education (NCPFECCE) for children up to the age of eight. NEP 2020 calls for setting up of a National Mission on Foundational Literacy and Numeracy by the Education Ministry. States will prepare an implementation plan for attaining universal foundational literacy and numeracy in all primary schools for all learners by grade 3 by 2025. A National Book Promotion Policy is to be formulated. All students will take school examinations in Grades 3, 5, and 8 which will be conducted by the appropriate authority. Board exams for Grades 10 and 12 will be continued, but redesigned with holistic development as the aim. A new National Assessment Centre, PARAKH (Performance Assessment, Review, and Analysis of

Knowledge for Holistic Development), will be set up as a standard-setting body. NEP emphasizes on setting up of Gender Inclusion Fund and also Special Education Zones for disadvantaged regions and groups. Every state/district will be encouraged to establish "Bal Bhavans" as a special daytime boarding school, to participate in art-related, career-related, and play-related activities. Free school infrastructure can be used as Samajik Chetna Kendras.

While implementing the reforms the NEP will only provide a broad direction and it's not mandatory to follow these directions. Since education is a concurrent subject (both the Centre and the state governments can make laws on it), the reforms proposed can only be implemented collaboratively by the Centre and the states. This will not happen immediately. The incumbent government has set a target of 2040 to implement the entire policy. Sufficient funding is also crucial; the 1968 NEP was hamstrung by a shortage of funds.

Though hopeful, we must not forget that the last time we tried to move some parts of the system by introducing a Continuous and Comprehensive Education in the K-12 system, we ended up in soup because of poor implementation structures. Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) was a process of assessment, mandated by the Right to Education Act, of India in 2009. In 2017, the CCE system was cancelled for students appearing in the Class 10 Board Exam for 2017-18, bringing back compulsory Annual Board Exam and removing the Formative and Summative Assessments under the Remodeled Assessment Pattern.

Emphasis On Mother Tongue/Regional Language For English-Medium Schools:

Such emphasis is not new: Most government schools in the country are doing this already. As for private schools, it's unlikely that they will be asked to change their medium of instruction. A senior ministry official clarified to The Indian Express that the provision on mother tongue as medium of instruction was not compulsory for states. "Education is a concurrent subject. Which is why the policy clearly states that kids will be taught in their mother tongue or regional language 'wherever possible'," the officer said.

People In Transferable Jobs, Or Children Of Multilingual Parents:

The NEP doesn't say anything specifically on children of parents with transferable jobs, but acknowledges children living in multilingual families: "Teachers will be encouraged to use a bilingual approach, including bilingual teaching-learning materials, with those students whose home language may be different from the medium of instruction."

Advantages And Disadvantages For Teachers:

A common National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST) will be developed by the National Council for Teacher Education by 2022, in consultation with NCERT, SCERTs, teachers and expert organizations from across levels and regions. States/UTs will set up independent State School Standards Authority (SSSA). The SCERT will develop a School Quality Assessment and Accreditation Framework (SQAAF) through consultations with all stakeholders. In fact, the change in curriculum framework for learners will directly impact the skills required by teachers and new curriculums for teacher education qualifications will be built to meet these needs.

Pre-service teacher education structures have been changed. A lot of underperforming teacher education institute or B.Ed. colleges might be shut down soon. NET-SET has already been replaced with PhD. So, it is suggested to a teacher aspirant to beware of where you enroll yourself. It'll be a good idea to start investing in short term courses on 21st century teaching skills to be ready for the upcoming change.

Government Plan To Open Up Higher Education To Foreign Companies:

The document states universities from among the top 100 in the world will be able to set up campuses in India. While

it doesn't elaborate the parameters to define the top 100, the incumbent government may use the 'QS World University Rankings' as it has relied on these in the past while selecting universities for the 'Institute of Eminence' status. However, none of this can start unless the HRD Ministry brings in a new law that includes details of how foreign universities will operate in India.

It is not clear if a new law would enthrone the best universities abroad to set up campuses in India. In 2013, at the time the UPA-II was trying to push a similar Bill, The Indian Express had reported that the top 20 global universities, including Yale, Cambridge, MIT and Stanford, University of Edinburgh and Bristol, had shown no interest in entering the Indian market.

Participation of foreign universities in India is currently limited to them entering into collaborative twinning programmes, sharing faculty with partnering institutions and offering distance education. Over 650 foreign education providers have such arrangements in India.

India is basically a country of farmers. This globalization aspect towards education would it affordable to the poor people certainly remains unresolved.

Privatization, Liberalization And Globalization:

An autonomous body, the National Educational Technology Forum (NETF), will be created to provide a platform for the free exchange of ideas on the use of technology to enhance learning, assessment, planning, administration. Private HEIs will be encouraged to offer larger numbers of free ships and scholarships to their students. NEP 2020 aims to increase the Gross Enrolment Ratio in higher education including vocational education from 26.3 per cent in 2018 to 50 per cent by 2035 and aims to add 3.5 crore new seats to higher education institutions. The policy envisages broad-based, multi-disciplinary, holistic Under Graduate education with flexible curricula, creative combinations of subjects, integration of vocational education and multiple entry and exit points with appropriate certification. Measures such as online courses and digital repositories, funding for research, improved student services, credit-based recognition of MOOCs, etc., will be taken to ensure distance learning is at par with the highest quality in-class programs. A comprehensive set of recommendations for promoting online education consequent to the recent rise in epidemics and pandemics in order to ensure preparedness with alternative modes of quality education whenever and wherever traditional modes of education are not possible, has been covered. A dedicated unit for the purpose of orchestrating the building of digital infrastructure, digital content and capacity building will be created in the HRD ministry to look after the e-education needs of both school and higher education. Internationalization of education will be facilitated through both institutional collaborations, and student and faculty mobility and allowing entry of top world ranked universities to open campuses in India. Stand-alone technical universities, health science universities, legal and agricultural universities etc. will aim to become multi-disciplinary institutions. Policy aims to achieve 100% youth and adult literacy. The Centre and the States will work together to increase the public investment in Education sector to reach 6 per cent of GDP at the earliest.

On the contrary, government schools are reducing in number. The of private schools are increasing rapidly in numbers. The general public is left with only one option to seek education in private schools and colleges, wherein, its not at all affordable to them, moreover, not assuring jobs in future. The new aspect of vocational education exists today such as Bachelor-of-Vocational the skill development degree course wherein MOUs are signed with industries which are supposed to look after training and placement of students. Here the question still arises whether these industries really

offer placements to students, whether students really become entrepreneurs. Additionally, it is observed that after employee retires from government posts it has not been recruited with new faculty. This is the reason for increase in jobless literate people throughout our nation.

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